

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING SANOGENIC THINKING AMONG STUDENTS IN SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Organizing classes with creative tasks, entertaining exercises, and playful situations contributes to developing students' healthy thinking, increasing physical activity and concentration, and reducing psycho-emotional stress in school education. Ensuring an effective learning process and creating hygienic and medical conditions facilitate easier problem-solving in educational processes.*

Keywords: *sanogenic, medical, stress, spiritual, physiological, hygienic, cognitive.*

Аннотация. *Организация занятий с творческими заданиями, увлекательными упражнениями и игровыми ситуациями способствует развитию здорового мышления учащихся, повышению физической активности и концентрации внимания, а также снижению психоэмоционального стресса в школьном образовании. Обеспечение эффективного учебного процесса, создание гигиенических и медицинских условий облегчают решение возникающих в образовательном процессе проблем.*

Ключевые слова: *саногенный, медицинский, стресс, духовный, физиологический, гигиенический, когнитивный.*

Using health-saving technologies during various lessons in school education contributes to creating a psychologically healthy classroom environment and increasing interest in subjects. Therefore, it is crucial to alternate different types of activities and apply methods that stimulate students' initiative and creative expression. Especially in biology lessons, creating an emotional atmosphere and motivational situations at the lesson's outset is essential for achieving success.

Visualization, creative tasks, entertaining exercises, playful situations, and various forms of lessons enhance cognitive and communicative abilities, imagination, physical activity, and concentration, reducing psycho-emotional stress. Engaging students in creative processes decreases their fatigue levels. Utilizing computer technologies further increases students' interest and improves their understanding of the material.

A healthy lifestyle has not yet occupied the top position in our society's hierarchy of needs and values. However, by teaching children to value, protect, and strengthen their health from an early age and demonstrating a healthy lifestyle through personal example, we can hope future generations become healthy individuals who are spiritually, intellectually, and physically developed. Observations show that using health-saving economical technologies in education helps students successfully adapt to the educational and social environment, discover creative abilities, and enables teachers to prevent antisocial behavior effectively.

The use of health-saving technologies helps address the following issues:

- Creating optimal educational conditions: hygienic, medical, etc.;
- Ensuring an effective learning process;
- Providing school students with meals during their time at educational institutions;
- Forming a culture of health at school;

- Providing professors and teachers with information on health culture, retraining, and professional development;
- Ensuring a healthy educational environment for students and teachers;
- Monitoring students' health conditions;
- Establishing thematic classes for teachers, students, parents, etc.

During the process of forming children's sanogenic abilities in classes, we adhere to a structure that includes identifying the problem, choosing methods to solve it, testing hypotheses proposed by students, forming conclusions, and recording results. Such an algorithm activates students' mental activities and encourages independent research. The teacher's primary role is not merely information transmission but facilitating its assimilation and guiding students towards health-oriented problem-solving.

Topics of lessons developed on this issue allow us to address several pedagogical problems: promoting cognitive development, providing a specific amount of knowledge about human anatomy, physiology, and hygiene, strengthening hygiene skills, creating motivation for learning, adhering to fundamental principles of a healthy lifestyle, developing logical thinking, and encouraging independence in behavior and learning.

The method of self-checking is essential for research activities. For instance, when studying the human musculoskeletal system, students determine the number of bones in skeletal sections, closely examine their hands under bright lamp illumination, and compare them with provided diagrams of human and animal limb structures.

Research activities help them understand the skeleton as the foundation of the human body, supporting and protecting all organs. Students not only learned about its significance for health but also created their own exercise sets for different body parts, illustrated them, and used them as physical exercises.

Guiding future teachers to apply these exercises effectively during pedagogical practice creates conditions for maintaining student health and developing in a healthy environment at schools.

In psychology, there's a belief that neglecting students' psychophysical and moral health causes acquired knowledge to lose value. Therefore, developing future teachers' sanogenic thinking aids in improving children's mental health and optimizing the overall pedagogical process in their future professional activities.

Just as students have unique psychophysical characteristics, teachers also differ. A teacher's activities reflect their professional competence and their physical, intellectual, and social well-being, overall and pedagogical cultural levels, and personal qualities. About 95% of students dropping out are related to poor health, often due to ignorance, indifference, and even cruelty by people responsible for instilling intellect and kindness. Thus, the primary goal in developing sanogenic thinking in future teachers is to shape students' abilities to maintain their health during education. The healthy mindset of teachers and students' interconnected sanogenic thinking play a crucial role in this regard.

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